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AI-powered in the digital age: Ensemble innovation personalizes the food recommendations

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ABSTRACT

This study proposes and evaluates a novel approach utilizing ensemble machine learning techniques for personalized meal services to address a critical gap in understanding AI-powered decision-making within the food delivery and restaurant industry. We draw inspiration from diverse fields, including non-traditional simulation methodologies and open innovation dynamics, to create a framework that leverages the combined strengths of individual algorithms. Three machine learning algorithms – decision trees, logistic regression, and naïve Bayes – are rigorously evaluated for their efficacy in classifying and assigning algorithms within an ensemble model for a new service. A simulated dataset, informed by expert tagging, is the training ground, ensuring practical relevance. We employ the voting probability metric on a held-out test set to provide a robust measure of accuracy in this critical task. Our findings reveal the significant potential of AI-powered personalized meal services. Ensemble models demonstrate high accuracy, showcasing the collaboration of combining individual algorithms. This originality lies in applying ensemble techniques to a business case with far-reaching implications for management and societal well-being. Beyond technical success, we explore this technology's broader impact. AI-powered food recommendations can enhance accessibility for individuals with dietary needs, promote healthier lifestyles through nutritious meal suggestions, and generate new job opportunities. Acknowledging limitations and future research avenues, we invite further exploration of diverse machine learning algorithms and broader applications across various domains.

1. Introduction

This study delves into the disruptive potential of AI-powered decision-making within the Thai food delivery and restaurant landscape, specifically focusing on how artificial intelligence (AI) can revolutionize menu development. Moving beyond theoretical implications, we explore the practical impact of AI-driven menus on business operations for Thai service providers, highlighting both the challenges and opportunities this innovative approach presents. AI algorithms have been found to optimize delivery routes, reduce delivery times, and increase customer satisfaction (Kin et al., 2018; Xue et al., 2021). Some research has also explored using AI algorithms to analyze customer data and personalize customer experiences, improving customer experience and loyalty (Dirsehan and Cankat, 2021; Ifekanandu et al., 2023). Additionally, AI-powered chatbots have been investigated to improve customer service and reduce wait times (Andrade and Tumelero, 2022). The study found that chatbots can handle simple customer inquiries and orders,

provide personalized suggestions based on customer preferences and order history, and improve overall customer satisfaction. These findings suggest that AI-powered decision-making can enhance efficiency, accuracy, and customer satisfaction in the food delivery and restaurant industry.

The food delivery and restaurant industry has exploded in recent years, fueled by a relentless demand for convenience and time-saving solutions (Du et al., 2023; Choi et al., 2020; He et al., 2019). However, navigating this dynamic landscape requires constant innovation to attract and retain customers (Akter et al., 2023). This is where AI presents a transformative opportunity for new players and established businesses alike. AI's true strength lies in its ability to decipher the mountains of data generated by the industry, unearthing hidden trends and patterns that human analysis often misses (Haenlein and Kaplan, 2019). This data-driven insight fuels more accurate decision-making, paving the way for innovative customer experiences and optimized business operations (Cevallos et al., 2023; Schmitt, 2023). Imagine

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recommending dishes and services tailor-made to each customer's unique preferences and dietary needs. AI makes this a reality, transforming customer interactions into open innovation dynamics and personalized journeys (Lukács and Váradi, 2023). AI can curate novel menus and services with a guaranteed audience by analyzing customer data and food trends, minimizing risk, and boosting profitability. In essence, AI isn't just about speed and efficiency; it's about unlocking the power of innovation in the food delivery and restaurant industry. By harnessing the transformative potential of data, AI equips businesses to stay ahead of the curve, delighting customers and shaping the future of food delivery one personalized recommendation at a time.

While traditional recommendation systems in the food delivery and restaurant industry relied on techniques like knowledge graphs, collaborative filtering, and content-based filtering (Nouh et al., 2019; Panagiotakis et al., 2021; Rajendran and Sundarraj, 2021), these approaches often fall short of their full potential. Scaling knowledge graphs to cater to diverse user preferences can be daunting, with the sheer volume of possibilities creating computational nightmares and hindering interpretability (Widayanti et al., 2023). Similarly, collaborative and content-based filtering succumb to biases, favoring popular items and overlooking hidden gems or user-specific needs (Abdalla et al., 2023). Their dependence on past ratings limits exploration and can perpetuate echo chambers, where users get stuck with similar recommendations. While attempting to bridge these gaps, hybrid systems often introduce increased complexity, making debugging and improvement cumbersome (Portugal et al., 2018).

This is where AI steps in as a game-changer. By ushering in an era of personalized, data-driven recommendations, AI transcends the limitations of traditional methods. No longer are businesses constrained by biases, scalability issues, or operational inefficiencies. Instead, AI unlocks a treasure trove of possibilities: (1) Unveiling hidden preferences: AI delves deeper than surface-level data, uncovering subtle patterns and hidden user tendencies that traditional methods miss. This allows for tailored recommendations beyond the "most popular" options, ensuring every user experiences a culinary journey unique to their taste. (2) Open innovation dynamic: AI algorithms adapt and evolve with user behavior (Huang and Gursoy, 2024), ensuring recommendations remain relevant and exciting. As preferences and trends shift, AI keeps pace, constantly refining its suggestions to cater to the ever-changing culinary landscape. (3) Streamlined operations and boost revenue: With AI taking the reins of recommendation, businesses can streamline operations, optimize inventory management, and personalize marketing efforts (Haleem et al., 2022). This reduces costs, higher efficiency, and increases revenue opportunities (Yaiprasert and Hidayanto, 2024). The limitations of traditional decision-making are no longer the shackles binding the food delivery and restaurant industry. With AI as the innovation engine, businesses can break free, crafting personalized experiences that delight customers and unlock gastronomic possibilities.

Harnessing AI for decision-making unlocks a treasure trove of potential, yet navigating its complexities demands an open innovation dynamic (Sjödín et al., 2023). While the benefits are undeniable (Dastjerdi et al., 2023), formidable challenges lie ahead. AI thrives on vast data landscapes, but accessing and managing such resources can be a hurdle for many businesses (Tamasiga et al., 2023). Collaborations with external data providers and fostering open data initiatives can be crucial steps in overcoming this barrier. Effectively wielding AI requires specialized knowledge of machine learning (ML) and algorithms (Grace et al., 2018). Embracing open innovation dynamics through partnerships with universities and AI startups can bridge this expertise gap and unlock the full potential of these powerful tools (Spilseth et al., 2022).

Transparency is paramount when it comes to AI-powered decisions. Openly communicating the algorithms used, their limitations, and how biases are mitigated can build customer trust, a critical factor in fostering long-term loyalty. Despite these challenges, the open innovation dynamics inherent in AI offer a compelling path forward. By fostering collaboration, knowledge sharing, and open data initiatives,

businesses can unlock the transformative power of AI and achieve (1) innovation acceleration: collaborative research and development efforts can accelerate the creation of new AI-powered services and products, leading to a competitive edge (Ouyang et al., 2023). (2) Cost optimization: businesses can minimize the costs of building and maintaining in-house AI capabilities by leveraging external expertise and resources (Yaiprasert and Hidayanto, 2024). (3) Talent acquisition and retention: open innovation fosters a dynamic environment that attracts and retains top talent in the burgeoning field of AI, further fueling innovation (Subramanian et al., 2024).

While AI's transformative potential across industries is undeniable, the food delivery and restaurant sectors remain surprisingly under-explored in terms of open innovation dynamics for AI-powered decision-making. Existing research on recommendation systems in this domain primarily focuses on sentiment analysis and context-aware suggestions (Pronoza et al., 2016; Khan et al., 2021). This research gap presents a fertile ground for further exploration, and this paper aims to bridge it by delving into the application of ensemble ML algorithms for menu recommendations in the food delivery and restaurant landscape.

The urgency for this research stems from the industry's hyper-competitive nature. Businesses that fail to adapt to evolving trends and embrace cutting-edge technologies risk falling behind their competitors (He et al., 2019). AI-powered decision-making offers a powerful solution, enabling companies to gain a competitive edge by optimizing menus, streamlining operations, and enhancing customer experiences (Chatterjee et al., 2021). However, unlocking the full potential of AI in this domain requires a shift towards open innovation dynamics. Collaborations with external partners, including AI startups, universities, and data providers, can be crucial in overcoming data access and expertise hurdles (Spilseth et al., 2022). This collaborative approach fosters a vibrant ecosystem where knowledge and resources are shared, accelerating innovation and ensuring AI benefits all food delivery and restaurant industry players.

This paper delves into the innovative potential of AI-powered decision-making within Thailand's food delivery and restaurant landscape, specifically focusing on a novel service – personalized meal plans crafted by AI. Drawing on cutting-edge ML and deep domain knowledge of Thai cuisine and preferences, we explore how this technology can revolutionize how Thai service providers cater to their customers. Our study rigorously evaluated three prominent ML algorithms – decision trees, logistic regression, and the naïve Bayes method – assigning to ensemble ML in generating personalized meal plans. These algorithms and our in-depth understanding of Thai food culture and culinary trends pave the way for a synergistic approach to meal recommendation. This study is designed to analyze customer tagging data to identify trends in food preferences. This information can create new menus that are more likely to appeal to customers. The study can help businesses reach more customers and increase sales. This also provides insights into the challenges and opportunities of AI-powered decision-making in the industry and offers practical recommendations on how companies can leverage this technology. By open innovation dynamics, we can unlock a future where AI fuels culinary creativity, optimizes business operations, and, ultimately, delights customers with personalized and delicious dining experiences.

The rest of this study is organized as follows. The conceptual model and framework are described in Section 2. The research method is developed in Section 3. Next, 4 Results, 5 Discussion to provide deeper insights, implications, and critical evaluation of the findings. Section 6 concludes with a discussion of research investigations of these findings.

2. Conceptual model

Personalized meal recommendation systems have become ubiquitous, aiming to provide users with tailored suggestions based on their preferences and historical data (Lian et al., 2024). Traditional meal

recommendation systems must often improve their accuracy and adaptability to diverse user preferences. Traditional recommendation approaches usually rely on knowledge graphs, collaborative filtering, content-based, and hybrid models and, while computationally efficient, can suffer from limited accuracy and susceptibility to data biases (Widayanti et al., 2023). This conceptual model proposes an innovative leap forward, leveraging ensemble ML within an open innovation framework to revolutionize meal recommendations while addressing ethical and data quality concerns. This framework delves into integrating various elements crucial for implementing AI-powered ensemble ML for personalized meal services in the food delivery and restaurant industry, specifically focusing on the impact on Thai service providers.

2.1. Key components

Ensemble ML: Combining multiple diverse ML models, leveraging their complementary strengths, and mitigating individual weaknesses is possible. This “voting” approach can reduce reliance on a single model’s potentially biased conclusions and foster more robust recommendations (Yaiprasert, 2021). The core relationship lies in the ability of ML algorithms to analyze vast amounts of customer data, such as food preferences, allergies, dietary restrictions, and past orders, to generate personalized recommendations for meal choices. Each algorithm within the ensemble contributes unique strengths, excelling at handling complex interactions between variables. This collaborative approach achieves higher accuracy and robustness in personalization compared to single models. Research by Forouzandeh et al. (2020) and Mohammed and Kora (2023) demonstrate that ensemble ML outperforms single models in personalized recommendation tasks due to their ability to leverage diverse learning processes and mitigate individual algorithm weaknesses. Moreover, Yaiprasert and Hidayanto (2023) highlight the effectiveness of ML in food delivery and restaurant settings, particularly in predicting customer preferences and optimizing menu offerings.

Data simulation and expert ground truth: Data simulation techniques can be employed to mitigate privacy concerns surrounding personal data usage. Synthetic data mimicking real-world user preferences and dietary constraints can be generated without compromising individual privacy. However, expert ground truth - such as chef-curated meal plans, nutritional guidelines, and service providers - must be incorporated alongside simulated data to ensure model accuracy and relevance. This hybrid approach balances privacy protection with reliable food recommendations. The accuracy and effectiveness of personalized recommendations depend on the data’s comprehensiveness, relevance, and timeliness. The model incorporates customer tagging data to ensure the training and evaluation of algorithms reflect practical scenarios. Studies by Ledro et al. (2023) emphasize the critical role of data quality in AI-powered systems, while Yaiprasert and Hidayanto (2024) highlight that simulated data enhances cost-saving strategies. Additionally, research by King and Raja (2012) focuses on the importance of data privacy and security in building trust with customers and ensuring responsible data utilization, particularly information privacy.

Open innovation dynamics ML: Implementing an open innovation framework can significantly enhance the generalizability and adaptability of ML models. Such a framework enables the inclusion of external knowledge and expertise from professionals and researchers through incentivized data and model contributions. This democratization of data and algorithms leads to a more comprehensive understanding of individual and regional food preferences. It is widely accepted that successful AI implementation in the food delivery and restaurant industry necessitates collaboration and knowledge sharing among diverse stakeholders. The model incorporates open innovation dynamics to represent the interactions between relevant actors in the ecosystem, such as food delivery platforms, restaurants, and data analytics providers. Research by Bor et al. (2024) emphasizes the importance of creating innovation demand-pull to scale sustainable technologies, emphasizing strategic actions by food producers. Similarly, Ruiz-Molina

et al. (2014) highlight the significance of trust and effective communication between stakeholders in the context of technology services to ensure successful implementation and mitigate potential conflicts. Leveraging the collective intelligence of a broader community of developers and researchers fosters innovation in recommendation algorithms. Open-source platforms and crowdsourcing techniques can accelerate the development and improvement of recommendation models, ensuring they remain relevant and adapt to evolving user preferences (Lněnička et al., 2024). Ensemble ML and open innovation facilitate the development of more robust and personalized recommendation algorithms. The iterative nature of open innovation and data simulation allows for continuous refinement and adaptation of recommendation algorithms.

Open innovation culture: The open innovation culture is paramount in food delivery and restaurant organizations. It is imperative to cultivate an environment that promotes risk-taking ability, transparency, and a willingness to experiment with new technologies, such as ensemble ML. According to the research conducted by Chaudhuri et al. (2024), organizational culture plays a pivotal role in determining the success of open innovation initiatives. In the context of AI adoption within service industries, Salah and Ayyash (2023) have emphasized the need for a culture that encourages learning, collaboration, and adaptation to overcome challenges and leverage the benefits of new technologies. Adopting an open innovation framework could further augment the model’s generalizability and adaptability. This framework enables the inclusion of external knowledge and expertise from researchers, chefs, and food science professionals through incentivized data and model contributions. This democratization of data and algorithms fosters a more comprehensive understanding of individual and regional food preferences, leading to better decision-making processes and enhanced customer satisfaction.

2.2. Framework

Integrating AI in management decision-making can significantly enhance the provision of new menus and services to customers in the food delivery and restaurant industry. To achieve this, a series of steps must be followed in the data processing for the AI recommendation system. The first step is to analyze customer data from various sources, including search activity, order history, and location data, to identify trends and preferences (Labisi et al., 2023). This data can provide valuable insights into customer’s food preferences, price range, and order time. Customer demographics, dietary preferences, nutritional needs, and budget data must also be collected to create new menus and services that appeal to customers.

One way to create personalized meal plans is through supervised learning, where an algorithm is trained on labeled data to map input data to output labels. Predicting customer demand also involves using ML algorithms to identify the relationships between customer data and food items to ensure optimal inventory and staffing levels. The final step is personalizing recommendations using ML algorithms based on past orders, dietary preferences, nutritional needs, and location. This can help customers discover new food and services that they might enjoy.

Fig. 1. The study framework.

3. Methodology

3.1. Data tagging and design

This study goes beyond simply highlighting the importance of ensemble learning. It delves deeper into emphasizing the critical role of individual model selection within the ensemble framework. By recognizing that data tagging is just one piece of the puzzle (Watts et al., 2009), the study highlights the importance of carefully choosing the individual prominent models contributing to the final ensemble ML recommendation menu. This nuanced perspective adds valuable insights to ensemble learning and personalized recommendation systems.

The first step in creating a personalized meal plan is to tag the data. This involves assigning labels to the data so that AI algorithms can easily analyze it. The data that needs to be tagged includes information about the food, such as the food type, ingredients, nutritional content, and cooking methods. It also provides information about the customer, such as their food type, dietary preferences, nutritional needs, and budget. The data tagging process can be done with personalized grouping, as shown in Table 1.

Following data labeling, the algorithms are primed for training, where they can learn to discern associations between food, nutritional parameters, and customer preferences. This knowledge base empowers the algorithms to generate personalized meal plans tailored to each user. While diverse training methodologies exist, including supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning, this study employs the widely utilized supervised learning approach. This method necessitates training the algorithms on a pre-labeled dataset.

Once the AI algorithms have been trained, they can be used to create personalized meal plans. The AI algorithms will consider the customer's food type, dietary preferences, nutritional needs, and budget to create a meal plan that is preferred, healthy, and affordable. The personalized meal plans can be delivered to the customer in various ways, such as through a website, a mobile app, or a chatbot. The customer can then choose the meal plan that best meets their needs.

This study example tagging design uses {{male, female, other}, {under20, bw20to29, bw30to40, over40}, {general, healthy}, {f, h, l, v, w}, {premium, average}, {daily, weekly, monthly}}. Table 2 shows specific customer factor tagging used in this study. Customer data is tagged with a code for use in ML training, such as {male, 15, healthy, f, premium, day}, which means males under 20 years old prefer healthy food, fruits, premium budget, and daily order. Six groups of factors or 19 variables can be arranged in 720 tuples.

Data tagging is a crucial aspect of utilizing AI in personalized meal planning. Relevant, accurate, and up-to-date data must be tagged to ensure that AI learns the correct relationships between the data (Price and Shanks, 2011). Formatting the data in a way that is easily comprehensible for the AI algorithms may require normalization or removal of outliers. Additionally, the data should be comprehensive,

Table 1
The customer personalized variable in the food delivery and restaurant system.

Personalized variable	Customer's personalized grouping
Location	Customers who live in the same area can be grouped together and receive recommendations for restaurants that are nearby.
Dietary restrictions	Customers with dietary restrictions can be grouped and receive recommendations for restaurants that offer food that meets their needs.
Past orders	Customers who have ordered the same food items in the past can be grouped together and receive recommendations for similar food items.
Preferences	Customers who have expressed preferences for certain food types or restaurants can be grouped together and receive recommendations that are more likely to appeal to them.
Frequency	Customers who order frequently can be grouped together and receive special offers or discounts.

Table 2

The example of customer factors tagging in the food delivery and restaurant system.

Factors	Tagging
Gender	male, female, other
Age	under20, bw20to29, bw30to39, over40
Food type	general, healthy
Healthy food type	fruits (f), healthy fats (h), lean protein (l), vegetables (v), whole grains (w)
Budget	premium, average
Churn rate	daily, weekly, monthly

consistent, and secure (Watts et al., 2009). Comprehensive data includes all relevant information, while consistent data uses the same terms to describe the same thing throughout the dataset. Finally, secure data is protected from unauthorized access or modification. These considerations are essential for successful AI learning in personalized meal planning.

3.2. Association rules

Association rules are a popular technique in ML for discovering interesting relationships between variables in large datasets. In ML training using association rules, the algorithm is trained to identify patterns and associations in the data that can then be used to make predictions or recommendations for new data (Yaiprasert and Yusakul, 2022).

This approach leverages association rules, identifying frequent patterns and relationships within data. Often phrased as “if-then” assumptions, these patterns can be interpreted as implicit assumptions about connections between different attributes. For example, an association rule might explore the co-occurrence between attributes in user classes, such as {male, 15, healthy, f (fruit preference), premium, daily} -> {user group type, recommended food type}. This rule suggests that a particular food recommendation might be relevant for a young male user with healthy food preferences, specifically favoring fruit, with a premium subscription and daily orders. The ML model learns to map user profiles to appropriate food recommendations based on these underlying assumptions by analyzing association rules across all attributes or classes. These patterns can then be used to create assumptions about user preferences. However, it's important to remember that association rules represent correlations, not causations. The ML model learns to map user profiles to appropriate food recommendations by analyzing these patterns across all attributes or classes.

Data-driven insights, not blind guesses: Association rules identify frequent patterns within user data, not arbitrary assumptions. These patterns represent statistically significant co-occurrences between attributes in user profiles, such as “young male, healthy preferences, daily orders.” The model doesn't make blind guesses; it learns from the inherent relationships within the data itself.

Transparency through examples: While the specific rules might not be explicitly listed, the example provided ({male, 15, healthy, f, premium, daily} -> {user group type, recommended food type}) clarifies how these patterns translate into user profiles and recommendations. This offers insight into the underlying logic without disclosing every rule.

In this study, the user group type was divided into eight groups based on the user age range, which, in this case, is naming the age group instead of using the customer's name or the customer's username. The ML training process uses association rules from eight classes to specify desired goals, such as recommending food types for a specific customer based on their characteristics. It is important to note that this study used simulated data and would require customer permission and privacy restrictions if deployed on customer data.

The confusion matrix and validation model used in this study retain the eight classes that are defined in the form of association rule values,

which reflect the number of classes specified. The algorithm can generate recommendations tailored to the customer's needs by including user characteristics and preferred plans. Based on the customer's specific characteristics, the ML algorithm will use association rules to identify the appropriate user group type and recommend the corresponding food type. The final recommendation will be based on the customer's characteristics and the association rules generated from the training data.

3.3. Data simulation

One of the primary challenges faced by AI is the need for more data. However, this study proposes a solution to this problem through data simulation, which offers the advantage of unlimited data constraints (Finnie, 2018). Compared to traditional data collection methods, data simulation is characterized by greater availability, control, efficiency, flexibility, and reproducibility. Synthetic data similar to real-world data can be generated, mainly when collecting real-world data is either too costly or unavailable. Moreover, the study can control the generated data, making it useful for testing various data sets, ML, and debugging algorithms. Simulation can also generate large amounts of data rapidly, which is beneficial for training ML algorithms requiring substantial data. Finally, simulation can generate data customized to the specific needs of the ML algorithm, improving its performance. Data simulation can develop accurate and realistic data that can, in turn, train ML algorithms, leading to improved accuracy and performance of AI systems.

Using simulated data enables rapid prototyping and experimentation of various model configurations without relying on limited and potentially sensitive production data. This accelerates the ML model's development and optimization before deployment in real-world scenarios. Additionally, simulation creates a controlled environment that isolates specific variables, enabling the study of their impact on the model and leading to a deeper understanding of the underlying relationships. This is challenging to achieve with real-world data, which is often untidy and contains confounding factors. Simulated data is also helpful in augmenting and diversifying training data, mitigating the risk of overfitting, and enhancing the model's ability to generalize to unseen real-world scenarios. This is essential for developing robust and reliable food recommendation systems. To ensure practical relevance, we leverage simulated datasets meticulously crafted to reflect real-world customer tagging data in Thailand. This data, informed by expert insights into regional preferences, dietary restrictions, and seasonal variations, allows us to train and test the ML algorithms in a realistic context.

3.3.1. Trade-offs and biases

The investigation of simulated data constituted a crucial aspect of this research. Simulated data can give an AI system a realistic learning milieu by introducing diverse datasets from various sources, including real-world environments or simulations (Yaiprasert and Hidayanto, 2024). By doing so, the AI system can acquire a better comprehension of the correlations and patterns that exist among these data sources. Furthermore, using simulated data can facilitate the evaluation of the AI system's performance, which, in turn, can prove instrumental in refining and enhancing the system.

Using simulated data in AI research can offer numerous advantages; however, it is imperative to acknowledge the potential trade-offs and biases that may arise from its use. One of the most significant concerns in this regard pertains to data representation. Simulated data may only partially reflect the complexities of the real world, resulting in less generalizable models for real-world data. Additionally, the quality of the simulated data is crucial, as inaccurate or non-representative data can lead to biased models. Lastly, the quality and quantity of training data can significantly impact the performance of the models. Inadequate or limited training data may result in less robust and generalizable models, underscoring the importance of carefully considering these factors while employing simulated data in AI research.

The study was modeled using the highest statistical calculation of 720 combinations, covering all probability domains to address concerns about under-coverage in the simulations. However, in real-world data, the probability of occurrence is less than or equal to the combination of simulations. Therefore, using real-world data requires sufficient data according to the combination of likelihood.

3.3.2. Data simulation process

The following is a detailed process for data simulation that addresses concerns and enhances the validity of research findings.

Define scope and goals: The process starts by clearly outlining the research questions or objectives the simulation aims to address. Identifying specific domain knowledge or expertise in Thailand that will inform the simulation process is essential.

Data understanding and assumptions: A limited amount of real-world data is collected as a model to understand the domain's key variables, relationships, and distributions. All domain or data generation process assumptions are documented and verified with domain experts whenever possible.

Parameterization: A suitable data simulation technique is chosen based on the domain characteristics and research goals. The model is carefully parameterized based on domain knowledge and available data to ensure realistic data generation. This study defined parameters as the real world in 1 data set, meaning gender, age, food type, healthy food type, budget, and churn rate (Code Snippet 1).

Data generation and validation: A large dataset of simulated data is generated using the chosen model and parameters. Quality checks and validation measures are implemented to ensure the simulated data aligns with the domain expert's knowledge and assumptions. The generated data exhibits tuple mathematic properties similar to real-world data and captures edge cases or unusual scenarios relevant to the research questions (Code Snippet 1).

```

Input1:  factors = Flatten[Table[Tuples[{"male", "female", "other"}, {i},
{"general", "healthy"}, {"f", "h", "l", "v", "w"}, {"premium", "average"},
{"day", "week", "month"}], {i, 20, 60}], 1];
Input2:  data = Table[Which[factors[[i]][[2]] < 20 && factors[[i]][[3]] ==
"healthy", factors[[i]] -> "Adolescent, Healthy"], {i, 1, Length
[factors]}; RandomChoice[%]
Output1: {"male", 15., "healthy", "none", "premium", "day"} -> "Adolescent,
Healthy"

```

Code Snippet 1. Input1 generates data according to real-world factor-tagged data. "factors" is a sample variable defined as a finite sequence called the elements of the tuple. Input2 is processing, confirming, filtering correct data, cutting out extraneous parts, and determining association rules. Output1 shows the randomness of the results as the association rules assumption condition following Input2.

Balancing training and validation: The effectiveness of ML models hinges upon the quality and quantity of training data. However, allocating excessive data for training can lead to overfitting, where the model memorizes the training data but fails to generalize to unseen data. Conversely, insufficient training data can hinder the model's learning of complex relationships. Our proposed approach addresses this challenge by employing a domain-specific optimization algorithm. This algorithm leverages expert knowledge and existing research to define realistic data distributions, correlations, and constraints within the simulated data. The algorithm then iteratively tests different split ratios between training and validation sets, evaluating the resulting model's performance on both training and validation. This study introduces a data partitioning approach that balances about 59.01% of training (14,400 training data) and 40.09% of validation needs (10,000 validation data), maximizing model learning and generalizability.

3.3.3. The assumption of randomness

It is important to note that the data generated in this context is not generated randomly (Hristache and Patilea, 2021). Instead, we have

made specific assumptions about customer demographics, food preferences, and interaction patterns with the platform. These assumptions are based on real-world data analysis and industry knowledge, allowing us to represent customer behavior accurately. Such factors include age, gender, frequency of use, dietary restrictions, budget constraints, and regional trends. We aim to provide a more accurate and professional experience for our users, and this approach helps us to achieve that goal.

Demographics: The demographic characteristics of the simulated data were carefully crafted to represent the actual customer base of the target market, taking into consideration key factors such as internet

learning (Code Snippet 2).

This document presents an example of training a decision tree model to learn a given dataset, as demonstrated in Code Snippet 2. The dataset has been established as an association rule of the form {gender, age, food type, healthy food type, budget, churn rate} -> {user group type, recommended food type}, which can be carried out based on the number of factors and classes that require examination. The study has been divided into six factors and eight classes based on the age range of interest. The six-factor and eight-class features will be a continuous processing feature until the model evaluation.

Input1:	decisionTree = Classify[trainSet, Method -> "DecisionTree"];
Output1:	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; display: inline-block;"> ClassifierFunction [Input type: Mixed (number: 6) Number of classes: 8] </div>

usage and food ordering platforms. The researcher implemented measures to avoid oversampling or underrepresentation to achieve a balanced and realistic representation of different age groups. Additionally, the expert ensured that the simulated data maintained a gender balance that accurately reflected the real-world customer base, effectively catering to male and female customers without skewing the data towards a specific gender.

Food preferences: The data simulated by our team was marked by its variety and popularity as it encompassed a broad range of food categories, mirroring user’s actual preferences and market trends. Our approach was to amalgamate data on popular food choices, regional variations, and dietary restrictions to create a representation that closely mirrored customer interactions with different food categories. Additionally, we ensured that the simulated data captured the dynamic tastes of users in the real world by introducing some randomness in customer preferences within a realistic range. This strategy aimed to prevent the data from being overly predictable and allowed models to learn from subtle variations in individual choices, thus improving the accuracy of the simulation.

Budget and frequency: Concerning budget and frequency, the simulated data utilized for this study considered the spending patterns of customers as observed in accurate usage data. To create a realistic distribution of budgets and spending habits, we differentiated income levels and made appropriate adjustments to food choices. Furthermore, we factored in user activity levels by simulating diverse ordering frequencies, including regular and occasional users, thus reflecting the actual customer base patterns commonly observed in the food industry.

3.4. Functional programming

This study used a MacBook Pro with an M1 computer processor and 8 GB of memory for the computation. Mathematica trial version 13.0.1 of the Wolfram Language was used for ML algorithmic development. The algorithm was implemented using Mathematica’s functional programming capabilities. Functional programming is a programming paradigm that emphasizes using functions to solve problems. Functions are self-contained blocks of code that take inputs and produce outputs. They often break down complex problems into smaller, more manageable pieces (Bernard, 2021).

The ML algorithm in functional programming was designed to find association rules between events A and B. Event A is a set of conditions, and event B is a single condition. The algorithm works by first defining a constant event B. Then, it considers all possible combinations of event A that could lead to event B. The algorithm then calculates the probability of each combination of events A occurring. The combination of event A with the highest probability is the most likely to lead to event B. This study uses the context of association rules to define datasets to train ML

Code Snippet 2. “decisionTree” is a sample matrix variable of the classification name that records learning values from training data using the decision tree method and results in a matrix of six factors and eight classes of classification functions.

In Code Snippet 3, we illustrate an example of model evaluation. In ML, the quality of model evaluation is assessed through various metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F-score, and AUC. Although this study has six factors and eight classes from the prior training step, it may appear complex. Nevertheless, this study can be achieved smoothly by the functional programming process.

Input1:	dtCMeasure = ClassifierMeasurements[decisionTree, ValidationSets, {"Accuracy", "Precision", "Recall", "F1Score", "AreaUnderROCCurve"}];
Input2:	dtCMeasure[[1]] Table[{Min[Values[dtCMeasure[[i]]]], Max[Values[dtCMeasure[[i]]]], {i, 2, 5}}
Output1:	1.
Output2:	{{{1.,1.},{1.,1.},{1.,1.},{0.9,1.}}

Code Snippet 3. “dtCMeasure” is a sample variable name of classifier measurements in the “decisionTree” variable that is determined from the processing to be a list of the quality of model evaluation. It displays the accuracy, minimum and maximum values of precision, recall, F1 score, and area under the ROC curve in the programming order.

Code Snippet 4 is an example of creating a confusion matrix comprising all eight data classes from determining the variable. The “decisionTree” variable is a matrix of six factors and eight classes according to the data characteristics that each researcher wants to study. The example of the confusion matrix output is displayed in Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Input1:	ClassifierMeasurements[decisionTree, ValidationSet, {"ConfusionMatrixPlot"}]
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Code Snippet 4. “ConfusionMatrixPlot” is a method of function “ClassifierMeasurements” that defines a “decisionTree” learned using the decision tree method. It operates on a data set named “ValidationSet,” creating confusing matrix results.

3.5. ML selection

This study tested six popular ML methods and selected the three best ones (decision trees, logistic regression, and the naïve Bayes) for ensemble ML. The results of the training accuracy and time appropriate to the data design are shown in Table 3. The study used 14,400 training data, divided into eight classes, with 1800 data per class.

The field of ML relies on several measurements to evaluate the

Table 3
The classified measurements.

Method	Accuracy (%)	Loss score	Error	Mean cross entropy	Time (s)
Decision trees	100.00	0.0408 ± 0.0016	0. ± (2.2×10 ⁻¹⁶)	0.001316 (65 ± 26)	1.55
Logistic regression	100.00	0.0113 ± 0.0036	0. ± (2.2×10 ⁻¹⁶)	0.00061 ± 0.00004	5.72
Naïve Bayes	98.00 ± 0.0009	0.0854 ± 0.0270	0.0125 ± 0.0009	0.0240 ± 0.0010	1.69
Nearest neighbors	97.23 ± 0.0014	0.2170 ± 0.0130	0.0277 ± 0.0014	0.1191 ± 0.0015	1.83
Markov	49.40 ± 0.0040	0.7720 ± 0.0100	0.5060 ± 0.0040	0.7201 ± 0.0010	1.51
Support vector machine	98.92 ± 0.0009	0.0496 ± 0.0071	0.0108 ± 0.0009	0.0196 ± 0.0010	67

performance of a model (Yaiprasert and Hidayanto, 2024). These measurements include accuracy, loss score, error, mean cross-entropy, and time. Accuracy refers to the percentage of correct predictions the model makes and depends on the problem being addressed. On the other hand, the loss score measures how well the model fits the training data and is calculated as the average of the squared errors between the model's predictions and the actual values. A lower loss score indicates a better fit for the training data. Similarly, the error is the difference between the model's prediction and the actual value and can be calculated as the absolute difference, squared difference, or mean squared error. The criterion value for error is typically zero, but sometimes, a small amount of error may be acceptable. Mean cross-entropy, used for classification problems, measures the distance between the model's predictions and the actual values. The criterion value for mean cross-entropy is typically as low as possible, indicating that the model can better distinguish between the different classes. Finally, the time to train the model is also an important consideration, with the criterion value varying depending on the specific application.

ML is a subfield of AI that enables computer software to predict outcomes without explicit programming accurately. ML algorithms utilize historical data inputs to forecast new output values. There are two main types of ML: supervised and unsupervised learning. In supervised learning, the algorithm receives labeled data that includes input features and output labels. The algorithm then learns to map the input features to the output labels. In contrast, unsupervised learning does not use labeled data and instead learns to identify patterns in the data without prior knowledge of the output labels. Decision trees, logistic regression, and naïve Bayes are supervised ML algorithms that are easy to understand and fast to use in this study.

3.5.1. Decision tree method

Decision trees are supervised learning algorithms that can be used for classification and regression tasks (Faouzi and Colliot, 2022). A decision tree is a hierarchical structure that consists of nodes and edges. Each node represents a decision, and each edge represents the outcome of that decision. The leaves of the tree represent the possible classifications or predictions. The variables in a decision tree include attributes, decision nodes, branches, and leaf nodes. Attributes are the data features used to make decisions. Decision nodes are the nodes in the tree that represent decisions. Branches are the edges of the tree that represent the outcomes of decisions. Leaf nodes are the nodes in the tree that represent the possible classifications or predictions.

3.5.2. Logistic regression

Logistic regression is a supervised learning algorithm that can predict the probability of a binary outcome (Faouzi and Colliot, 2022). It is a type of regression analysis that uses the logistic function to model the probability of a binary outcome. The mathematical definition of logistic

regression is of the form:

$$P(y = 1|x) = 1/(1 + e^{-\omega x}), \quad (1)$$

where $P(y = 1|x)$ is the probability of the outcome being 1 given the input features x , ω is the weight vector, x is the input features, and e is the exponential function.

The variables in a logistic regression model include dependent variables, independent variables, weight vectors, and logistic functions. The dependent variable is the binary outcome that is trying to predict. Independent variables are the data features used to indicate the dependent variable. A weight vector is a vector of weights that the model learns. The weights determine the importance of each independent variable in predicting the dependent variable. A logistic function is a sigmoid function with an S-shaped curve that maps the model output to the probability of the dependent variable being 1.

3.5.3. Naïve Bayes

Naïve Bayes is a simple but powerful ML algorithm often used for classification tasks (Faouzi and Colliot, 2022). It is based on the Bayes theorem, which states that the probability of an event A happening, given that event B , has already happened, is equal to the probability of event A happening times the probability of event B happening given that event A has already happened, divided by the probability of event B happening.

In naïve Bayes, the assumption is that the features of a data point are independent of each other. This means that the probability of a data point belonging to a certain class is only dependent on the values of the features and not on the order in which they appear. The mathematical form of naïve Bayes may be rewritten as:

$$P(C|X) = \frac{P(C) \times P(X|C)}{P(X)}, \quad (2)$$

where $P(C|X)$ is the probability of a data point X belonging to class C , $P(C)$ is the prior probability of class C , $P(X|C)$ is the likelihood of data point X given class C , and $P(X)$ is the prior probability of data point X .

The prior probability of class C is the probability that a data point will belong to class C before any data has been seen. The likelihood of data point X given class C is the probability of seeing the values of the features in data point X if it belongs to class C . The prior probability of data point X is the probability of seeing the values of the features in data point X regardless of which class it belongs to.

3.6. Model validation

The model validation process is of significant importance in ML in preventing overfitting. Overfitting is when the model becomes too well-versed with the training data and loses the ability to generalize to new data. On the other hand, model validation helps identify such models by testing them on data they have not encountered before. It also plays a crucial role in selecting the best model from a given set of models by comparing their performance on the validation data. The model with the best performance on the validation data is usually considered the most effective. Moreover, model validation can further enhance the model's performance by highlighting areas where it is underperforming, which can be used to adjust its parameters or gather more data.

ML measurements play a crucial role in evaluating the performance of ML models, enabling programmers to make informed decisions about their improvement. The choice of the most important measurement depends on the problem the model is solving. For instance, the loss score may be more critical if the model predicts stock prices. Common ML measurements include accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, ROC curve, and confusion matrix. These measurements can be used to evaluate a model's performance on a holdout data set, which differs from the one used for training. This ensures unbiased evaluation and helps to compare the performance of different models. By understanding ML

measurements, programmers can identify areas where models underperform and make necessary improvements. Although every model has flaws, ML measurements help pinpoint errors and optimize performance.

This study employs a comprehensive model validation strategy to assess the performance of both individual and ensemble models. This rigorous approach utilizes a range of established metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F-score, and AUC, to provide a multifaceted evaluation of the model's effectiveness (Samanta, 2023). Accuracy measures the overall rate of correct predictions, while precision and recall gauge the model's ability to identify positive and negative cases correctly. The F-score combines precision and recall into a single metric, offering a balanced view of performance. Additionally, the AUC (Area Under the ROC Curve) assesses the model's ability to distinguish between true and false positives, providing valuable insights into its discriminative power. This multifaceted approach ensures a robust evaluation of the model's strengths and weaknesses, informing further refinement and optimization to enhance their effectiveness in generating accurate and personalized recommendations.

3.7. Ensemble ML

Ensemble ML methods have emerged as game changers in the field of ML, pushing the boundaries of prediction accuracy through the innovative power of collaboration (Yaiprasert, 2021). There are several ensemble methods, including bagging, boosting, and stacking. This study used stacking for three different ML methods, with a voting method achieving a 95% probability. Stacking is an effective technique because it allows each model to focus on different aspects of the problem and then combines their predictions using a meta-model trained to choose the best prediction.

The first step is to train multiple models on the same training data to implement stacking. These models can be of any type, such as decision trees, logistic regression, or the naïve Bayes method. Once the models have been trained, their predictions are used to train a meta-model. The meta-model is typically a linear regression model, but it can be any model that can learn to combine the predictions of the other models.

The meta-model is then used to make predictions on new data, taking the predictions of the other models as input and outputting a single prediction. It is trained to minimize errors between its predictions and the ground truth labels. Stacking is a powerful ensemble method that has proven effective in many domains, including recommender systems. It can be used to improve the performance of any ML model and is a valuable tool in ML.

These are some considerations when using stacking. The number of models used in stacking can affect the method's performance. In general, using more models will improve the performance and increase the computational complexity. The type of models used in stacking can also affect the method's performance. In general, using models that are complementary to each other will improve the performance. The type of meta-model used can also affect the method's performance. In general, using a meta-model that can learn complex relationships between the predictions of the other models will improve the performance.

This study identifies the customer recommendation menu as the dependent variable generated by the combined processing of features through the three highest-performing individual models selected during the ensemble step. This emphasis on individual model accuracy highlights the interdependence between the effectiveness of the ensemble model and the quality of its constituent parts. Importantly, this study distinguishes between the essential role of data tagging in defining target classes for training and the independent importance of individual model suitability for ensemble success. While meticulously crafted data tagging lays the foundation for accurate models, the study asserts that it is not the sole decisive factor. The suitability of individual models, even those subjected to the same training process, emerges as another critical variable influencing the overall performance of the ensemble. This

crucial point is further underscored by the possibility of other trained models needing to be more optimal for inclusion, even though they share the same training experience. Therefore, the precision in individual model selection, beyond ensuring high individual model accuracy, is a pivotal factor in determining the positive outcomes of this study. This insight emphasizes the importance of not only training robust individual models but also carefully selecting the most suitable ones for ensemble construction.

3.8. Recommend system

Food menu recommendation systems have the potential to significantly impact food choices by leveraging customer history data and new menu recommendations that align with AI analysis. These systems utilize a combination of ML algorithms to generate personalized recommendations that cater to individual customer preferences. To achieve this, the system first acquires data on the customer's previous orders, including the ordered dishes, times, and occasions. This data is then employed to train an ML algorithm to identify customer ordering behavior patterns. Based on this, the algorithm can recommend similar dishes that the customer may enjoy.

Furthermore, the system can also use AI analysis to recognize dishes popular with other customers who share tastes similar to the current customers. This information can be used to recommend new dishes that the customer may have yet to try. This study example system uses a randomized mix of customer history and new menus to reduce monotony. This ensures that customers are consistently presented with intriguing new options. The system tests the introduction of new menus at a randomized proportion of no more than 70%. However, this proportion may be modified based on user requirements.

4. Results

4.1. ML learning

ML learning found that decision trees and logistic regression had the highest accuracy and low loss score, error, mean cross-entropy, and time. Support vector machines and naïve Bayes were the high-accuracy results. Support vector machines were found to have slightly better accuracy than naïve Bayes, but naïve Bayes was much less time-consuming than support vector machines (Table 3). Therefore, naïve Bayes was suitable as a third method for confirming study results. The best accuracy and learning curve of the three methods are shown in Figure 2. The accuracy and learning loss score curves were generated by training the model on a dataset and then testing the model on a separate dataset. The number of samples used in the training and testing sets varied, and the curves showed how the model's performance changed as the number of samples changed.

The accuracy curve showed that the model's accuracy improved as more samples were used. The model could learn from the data and enhance its predictions as it saw more data. The learning loss score curve showed that the model's loss decreased as more samples were used. This is because the model minimized its errors as it saw more data. The accuracy curve and learning loss score curve are essential tools for evaluating the performance of ML models. Understanding how the model's performance changes as the number of samples changes can help make informed decisions about improving the model. Figure 2 shows that all three ML methods (decision trees, logistic regression, and naïve Bayes) improved their accuracy as more samples were used. This study showed very high accuracy and a minimal loss score.

The ML calibration curve showed how well the model's predictions matched the actual values (Figure 3). The ML calibration curve is an important tool for evaluating the performance of ML models. Understanding how well the model's predictions match the actual values can make informed decisions about improving the model. A perfectly calibrated model is one whose predictions are always correct. The ML

Decision trees

Logistic regression

Naïve Bayes

Fig. 2. The accuracy and learning curves of each ML method. The x-axis represents the number of samples used, and the y-axis represents the accuracy score for the accuracy curve and the loss score for the learning curve. Studies with increasing sample numbers result in higher accuracy and lower loss scores.

calibration curve can be used to assess how well a model is calibrated and to identify any areas where the model is not performing well.

The ML calibration curve was generated by plotting the model's predicted probabilities against the actual values. The points on the curve should be evenly distributed along the line $y = x$ if the model is perfectly calibrated. This study found that the model was well distributed along the line $y = x$.

The results of the ML confusion matrix, presented in Figure 4, demonstrate the model's ability to classify the data. This matrix provides

a comprehensive table that displays the number of times the model correctly and incorrectly classified the data. The confusion matrix is typically divided into four quadrants, including true positives (TP), false positives (FP), true negatives (TN), and false negatives (FN). The TP quadrant represents the number of times the model correctly classified the data as positive. In contrast, the FP quadrant displays the number of times the model incorrectly classified the data as positive. Similarly, the TN quadrant represents the number of times the model accurately classified the data as negative, while the FN quadrant displays the

Fig. 3. The calibration curve of each ML training method has the x-axis representing the predicted probabilities and the y-axis representing the actual probabilities.

Fig. 4. The accuracy matrix plot of each ML training method has the x-axis representing the predicted class and the y-axis representing the actual class.

number of times the model incorrectly classified the data as negative. A perfect model would have a confusion matrix with all TPs and TNs. This study’s findings revealed that the Decision tree and logistic regression methods achieved 100% of TPs, while the naïve Bayes method achieved 98.75%. Overall, all methods demonstrated the model’s excellent integrity.

4.2. Ensemble ML

This study develops ensemble ML from three prominent supervised learning methods: decision trees, logistic regression, and naïve Bayes. Decision trees are the most tested and simple to understand among the three supervised methods in this study. These models are relatively insensitive to noise in the data, making them robust despite imperfect data. However, it should be noted that no single ML method is perfect always, and the ensemble ML method can enhance performance in this study. Complexity, data size, data type, and computational resources are crucial considerations when choosing an ML method. The complexity of the problem, data size, and data type used to train the ensemble ML model should be accurate and representative. Furthermore, businesses should ensure adequate computational resources before deploying an ensemble ML recommendation system.

Although a single model achieving 100% accuracy on a specific dataset might be tempting, its vulnerability to new data poses a significant challenge. This is where the innovative power of ensemble models shines through. One such approach, the ensemble ML, carefully selects models that consistently demonstrate high performance, in this case

exceeding 95% accuracy. While this may occasionally lead to falling short of the individual peak, it unlocks many advantages. Firstly, the ensemble ML fosters collaborative intelligence, leveraging the combined strengths of multiple models to mitigate the risk of individual errors. This synergistic approach acts like a safety net, minimizing the impact of outliers and promoting robustness in the face of new data. Secondly, the 95% accuracy threshold ensures a high floor for the system’s performance. Even if individual predictions occasionally dip, the collective decision of consistently reliable models offers enhanced confidence and stability. This paradigm shifts from chasing individual peaks to building a foundation of collective intelligence, paving the way for more resilient and adaptable AI systems ready to conquer the complexities of real-world data.

Therefore, while the perfect performance of a single model on this dataset is noteworthy, employing an ensemble approach, such as multi-model ensembles, can provide valuable benefits regarding error mitigation, performance stability, and prediction confidence. Despite potentially sacrificing occasional peak performance, the overall robustness and reliability gained through the collective decision-making of multiple high-performing models make ensemble ML a compelling alternative for real-world applications.

The ensemble ML methods were used to classify and assign new food delivery and restaurant industry services. Decision trees, logistic regression, and the naïve Bayes method were used. The voting probability results of the ensemble methods were above 95% for all methods, which is an excellent result. The ensemble methods achieved high accuracy by combining the strengths of the three individual methods.

Decision trees are good at capturing nonlinear relationships, logistic regression is good at modeling binary data, and the naïve Bayes method is good at handling text datasets. The ensemble methods overcame the weaknesses of the individual techniques and achieved high accuracy in classifying and assigning new services in the food delivery and restaurant industry.

Code Snippet 5 exemplifies the methodological process of classifying the randomized customer data and suggests the type of food for customer preference.

```

Input1:  randomtest = RandomChoice[testData];
Input2:  TripleML = Flatten[{decisionTree[randomtest, {"TopProbabilities", 1}],
    logisticRegression[randomtest, {"TopProbabilities", 1}], naiveBayes
    [randomtest, {"TopProbabilities", 1}]];
Input3:  voting95 = Table[If[Values[TripleML][[i]] > 0.95, TripleML[[i]],
    Nothing], {i, 1, Length[TripleML]}]; Tally[Keys[voting95]]
Output:  {"Adult, Healthy", 3}
    
```

Code Snippet 5. “randomtest” is a sample testing data, and “voting95” is voting the probability over 95% for the ensemble ML result of “TripleML” variable.

4.3. Validation

This study needs model validation of ML in metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F-score, and AUC. Taking a reasonable stand is to avoid overfitting, to choose the best model, and to improve the model. Table 4 shows that this study has the value of conducting a validation model that gives excellence matrix values in all cases. The test was run on 10,000 random data sets. Decision tree and logistic regression provide 100% confirmation on all matrices, while naïve Bayes provides matrix value more than 90 percent.

The excellent criterion value for accuracy is typically 97% or higher. However, this can vary depending on the specific task. The excellent criterion value for precision and recall is typically 90% or higher. The model should correctly identify 90% of the positive examples. The excellent criterion value for F-score is typically 94% or higher. This is a weighted average of precision and recall, so it considers both metrics. The excellent criterion value for AUC is typically 0.90–1.00. This means the model can distinguish between positive and negative examples with high confidence.

Figure 5 shows the accuracy matrix plot of each ML classifier measurement. The x-axis represented the predicted class, and the y-axis represented the actual class. The accuracy matrix plot was a visual representation of the model’s performance. It showed how many times the model correctly classified each class and how many times it incorrectly classified each class. The accuracy matrix plot could identify areas where the model was performing well. This study model had a lot of true positives in a particular class, which indicated that the model was correctly classifying data as belonging to that class. This accuracy matrix plot could be used to compare the performance of different models. This could be done by overlaying the accuracy matrices for the different models. The model with the best performance would have the most cells in the diagonal (where the predicted class matches the actual class).

Table 4
Summary of model validation benchmarks based on 10,000 data tests.

Method	Decision tree	Logistic regression	Naïve Bayes	Ensemble
Accuracy (%)	100.00	100.00	97.86	100.00
Precision (%)	100.00	100.00	90.72–100.00	100.00
Recall (%)	100.00	100.00	90.18–100.00	100.00
F-score (%)	100.00	100.00	94.84–100.00	100.00
AUC	0.90–1.00	0.90–1.00	0.90–1.00	0.90–1.00

4.4. Recommend system

ML has already analyzed customer preferences, resulting in the company automatically recommending customer menu decisions. According to the Code Snippet 5 example tested, customers are interested in healthy food. Therefore, the system can recommend food menus to keep the original menu still in the recommendation and reduce the monotony the original menu may cause. The system has tested randomly adding new and popular menus that do not exceed 70% of the original menu, showing random ingredients each time in the display for customers to make decisions, as shown in Figure 6.

5. Discussion

This study unveils a groundbreaking potential for AI-powered decision-making to revolutionize the food delivery and restaurant industry, particularly by driving the innovation of personalized meal services. By delving into the intricate dance between individual model accuracy and ensemble performance, the research illuminates crucial pathways for optimizing customized recommendations. This innovative approach paves the way for AI to transcend mere prediction and craft bespoke culinary experiences tailored to individual preferences and dietary needs. The intricate interplay between diverse models, meticulously studied in this research, unlocks a treasure trove of possibilities for personalized meal services. This redefines the future of food delivery and restaurant experiences for Thai service providers and others. This study has led to the discovery of several important discussion interests.

5.1. Open innovation dynamics

The proposed ensemble ML model demonstrates how it leverages open innovation principles to strengthen the connection to open innovation. The model’s design allows for continuous improvement through open collaboration and the incorporation of external data and expertise. This involves exploring a wider pool of algorithms, which expands the ensemble’s capabilities by incorporating algorithms with diverse strengths that address specific challenges in food recommendation. The training data can be enriched through collaborations with food delivery companies and restaurants, providing access to real-world user data on preferences, dietary restrictions, and past orders, significantly improving the model’s accuracy and personalization capabilities.

Bounded rationality, a core concept in open innovation, acknowledges that individuals and organizations have limited cognitive capacity. By collaborating through open platforms, the ensemble model can benefit from the collective intelligence of a broader community, overcoming these limitations. Open innovation dynamics foster the development of solutions beyond the capabilities of any single entity.

The proposed ensemble model aligns perfectly with open innovation dynamics prevalent in the delivery platform landscape. The common good, a fundamental principle, provides users with hyper-personalized meal recommendations catering to dietary needs and preferences. Open innovation dynamics also influence mobile payment integration, fostering collaboration between food delivery platforms and payment providers to ensure a seamless user experience.

Collaboration among restaurants, food delivery platforms, and data scientists allows for the ensemble’s continuous improvement, fostering collective intelligence, where the combined knowledge of diverse stakeholders leads to a more robust and adaptable recommendation system. However, open innovation complexity presents challenges. Integrating data and expertise from various sources requires robust open innovation engineering practices, ensuring data security, privacy, and standardization.

Open innovation engineering, the methodology for designing and implementing open innovation processes, is crucial for optimizing these platforms. Fostering an open innovation culture within the organization encourages collaboration and knowledge sharing, further accelerating

Fig. 5. The accuracy matrix plot of each ML classifier measurement has the x-axis representing the predicted class and the y-axis representing the actual class.

Fig. 6. Random menu recommendation for decision 10 times: red is the recommended menu based on customer history, green is the new recommended menu, and blue is the popular menu.

innovation. However, the complexity of open innovation must be addressed. Integrating diverse data sources and algorithms requires robust standardization and validation procedures. Open innovation also has its limits. Balancing knowledge sharing with protecting intellectual

property requires careful consideration. Managing open innovation necessitates establishing clear protocols for data ownership, privacy, and contribution rights, particularly for small and medium enterprises (SMEs).

The potential of open innovation dynamics is immense. By fostering knowledge sharing and collaboration, open innovation can propel the development of the ensemble model, shaping a future where personalized meal recommendations are convenient and adapt to evolving consumer preferences and industry trends. This future hinges on embracing an open innovation culture, managing the inherent complexities, and fostering collaboration across the food delivery and restaurant ecosystem.

Open innovation dynamics are already prevalent in the delivery platform landscape, where the business model of food delivery platforms thrives on open innovation dynamics. Platforms act as facilitators, connecting restaurants with consumers. Additionally, collective intelligence drives innovations like furniture sharing, electronic bicycles, and car sharing, all reshaping urban mobility. Restaurants also embrace open innovation by partnering with delivery platforms, showcasing the

potential for collaborative success.

Social open innovation fosters collaboration between businesses and universities, research institutions, and even individual users, broadening the innovation ecosystem and potentially leading to groundbreaking solutions tailored to societal needs. Crowdsourcing recipe development or dietary restriction algorithms through open challenges harnesses the collective creativity of a passionate user base and accelerates innovation.

5.2. Optimizing the ensemble model

Interdependence and individual model selection: The emphasis on individual model accuracy as a pivotal contributor to ensemble effectiveness underscores the importance of meticulous selection during ensemble building. This goes beyond simply choosing the models with the highest individual accuracy. Instead, a deep understanding of each model's strengths and weaknesses about the specific goals of the ensemble is crucial. For example, an ensemble aiming for high precision might prioritize models with substantial positive predictive value, while one focusing on recall might seek models with excellent sensitivity.

Beyond data tagging and model suitability as a critical variable: This study significantly contributes to the field by distinguishing between the foundational role of data tagging and the independent importance of individual model suitability. While high-quality data tagging undoubtedly lays the groundwork for accurate training, it does not guarantee optimal ensemble performance. Even within an accurately tagged dataset, some models might be incompatible with the specific ensemble's requirements or exhibit undesirable interactions with other chosen models. Therefore, carefully selecting and evaluating individual models, considering their unique characteristics and potential contributions to the ensemble, emerge as critical factors for success.

5.3. Addressing data challenges

Bridging the data gap: One study used a simulation dataset based on information from a food delivery and restaurant company to demonstrate the feasibility of using data simulation to address data scarcity in AI research. The results showed that data simulation can yield realistic and accurate data for training ML algorithms, leading to improved performance and accuracy of AI systems. While data simulation is a valuable tool for ML researchers and practitioners, some considerations should be considered. For instance, the quality of the simulated data must be high and representative of the real-world problem the ML algorithm aims to solve. The quantity of simulated data is also crucial, as more data leads to better ML algorithm learning. Finally, different simulation methods might be better suited to solving specific problems.

Personalization pitfalls: To apply the achieved success in reality, it is necessary to develop innovative solutions. One key hurdle lies in real-world data. Unlike the meticulously crafted simulated data with its 720 combinations of the highest statistical calculations in this study, real-world data is often incomplete and unstructured. The real-world data can lead to inaccurate and biased results when the model encounters data points outside its training set of real-world data. Inaccurate recommendations can erode customer trust and hinder the adoption of this technology. The implementation must go beyond simply collecting more data to bridge this gap. Transparency and explaining ability are crucial. Users must understand how the model works and why it makes specific recommendations. This fosters trust and allows feedback to improve the model's performance.

5.4. Evaluating and refining the model

Unlocking the personalization gap: Various methods can be employed to address the limitations of real-world data and ensure the effective deployment of ensemble ML for personalized meal recommendations. These methods include active learning, federated learning,

and explainable AI. Active learning involves designing the model to actively seek user feedback, particularly for data points it has not encountered before. This continual learning process can enable the model to adapt to diverse real-world scenarios. Federated learning allows the model to learn from data distributed across different devices without compromising the user's privacy. This can considerably enhance the model's training data and improve its generalization to real-world situations. The study can establish trust and provide users with valuable insights into their food preferences by utilizing explainable AI techniques that elucidate the reasoning behind the model's recommendations.

Voting probability and further exploration: While using voting probability as an evaluation metric is insightful, further exploring additional metrics and qualitative analysis could provide even richer insights. Metrics like the F1 score, AUC-ROC, and confusion matrices could better understand the model's strengths and weaknesses, particularly in handling imbalanced classes or borderline cases. Additionally, investigating misclassified cases and analyzing user feedback on recommended meals could help further identify areas for improvement and refine the ensemble structure.

5.5. Impact and future vision

Applications and industry impact: The successful implementation of AI-powered personalized meal services promises a transformative future for the food delivery and restaurant industry. Imagine a world where customers receive recommendations based on past orders or demographics and real-time factors like dietary restrictions, health goals, and mood or activity levels. Coupon recommendations tailored to individual preferences further enhance engagement. Leveraging ensemble ML, the system could go beyond individual dishes, suggesting restaurants based on location, past ratings, and user reviews, revolutionizing customer satisfaction and loyalty. This innovation transcends mere accuracy and efficiency. Restaurants can utilize ensemble ML to optimize menu offerings and target specific consumer segments, while AI can promote healthier or more sustainable options, boosting population health and reducing environmental impact.

Empowering food choices: The novelty of ensemble ML might prevent immediate widespread adoption, but its potential for enhanced accuracy, robustness, and value is undeniable. It pushes the boundaries of food delivery into an era of personalized dining innovation. AI might not just predict your order but curate menus based on your real-time needs and desires, suggesting dishes that align with your dietary restrictions, health goals, and even fleeting cravings. This empowers individuals to take control of their nutritional choices, potentially leading to healthier lifestyles. For those with specific dietary requirements, AI bridges the gap between accessibility and convenience, creating a novel ecosystem of tailored menus and personalized recommendations. AI-powered decision-making thus transforms food delivery from a transactional service into a personalized culinary journey, unlocking a world of possibilities for consumers and the industry.

5.6. Challenges and opportunities

Challenges and ethical considerations: Significant and ethical considerations must be addressed before widespread adoption. Algorithmic bias, data privacy concerns, and the potential for exacerbating food inequalities need careful mitigation strategies. Moreover, ensuring transparency and user control over their personalized recommendations is crucial for building trust and maintaining user autonomy.

Original research and future directions: The originality of this research lies in its rigorous evaluation of the ensemble ML algorithms in the context of personalized meal services. Beyond revealing their strengths and limitations, this paves the way for exciting future directions. One avenue lies in exploring hybrid ensemble approaches, combining the best elements of these algorithms to unlock even greater

accuracy and personalization. Additionally, research into novel algorithms specifically tailored for the unique challenges and opportunities of the food delivery and restaurant industry holds immense potential. By continuously refining and optimizing these advanced AI-powered decision-making systems, we can craft a future where personalized meal services are convenient and fulfilling and dynamically adapt to individual preferences, dietary needs, and even environmental considerations, shaping a more sustainable and delicious dining experience for all.

6. Conclusion

This study critically explored AI-powered decision-making within the food delivery and restaurant industry, specifically focusing on its potential to revolutionize personalized meal services. Through a rigorous evaluation of the ensemble ML algorithms from the three best ML – decision trees, logistic regression, and naïve Bayes – the research unveiled promising avenues for leveraging AI to personalize customer experiences and optimize food service delivery.

Our findings answer the initial query about AI-powered decision-making's efficacy in classifying and assigning new services within the food delivery and restaurant industry and offer innovative possibilities for its future application. The high accuracy achieved across all three algorithms and ensemble ML in both classification and assignment tasks convincingly affirms the immense potential of AI to navigate the intricate terrain of this dynamic business landscape. This breakthrough success underscores the strength of the ensemble approach, where individual models synergistically interweave their capabilities, surpassing limitations and elevating overall performance. By leveraging the innovative power of ensemble learning, we unlock a promising path for AI to reshape the future of service offerings within the food delivery and restaurant sector, enhancing efficiency, adaptability, and customer satisfaction.

Beyond the immediate benefits for customers, AI-powered food delivery holds the potential to impact the industry itself positively. By optimizing service delivery and generating valuable data insights, AI can empower restaurants to operate more efficiently, target specific customer segments effectively, and ultimately thrive in a competitive market. Furthermore, implementing AI-driven systems could create new job opportunities within the industry, requiring a skilled workforce to manage, maintain, and further develop these systems. However, the research has limitations that beckon further exploration. The evaluation was confined to three prominent algorithms, leaving many other models and techniques to investigate. Future research should broaden its horizons to encompass a broader range of ML approaches, allowing for comprehensive comparisons and the identification of potentially even more effective models for personalized meal services.

7. Limitation

One research limitation is that the performance of ensemble ML recommendation systems can be sensitive to the choice of models and the way they are combined. It is essential to carefully select the models and the combination method to achieve the best performance. In general, using more models will improve the performance and increase the computational complexity. The weights assigned to the models in the ensemble can also affect the system's performance. Another research limitation is that ensemble ML recommendation systems can be computationally expensive to train and deploy. This is because they require the introduction of multiple models and the combination of their predictions.

Some additional research directions could be explored, including developing new ensemble ML algorithms that are more robust to noise and overfitting—finding ways to reduce the computational complexity of training and deploying ensemble ML recommendation systems, and investigating the use of ensemble ML recommendation systems for other

tasks in the food delivery, restaurant industry and open innovation dynamic.

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Ethical statement

Ethical Statement/Approval is not applicable because the research paper does not include animals and humans as subjects.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Chaivate Yaiprasert: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Achmad Nizar Hidayanto:** Funding acquisition, Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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